

Fog-based AI image analysis for load disaggregation using Random Forest and XGBoost

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Abstract. The use of artificial intelligence to energy systems is growing, and image-based analysis is showing promise as a tool to improve optimization and monitoring. This paper presents a new load disaggregation architecture that improves responsiveness and efficiency by combining fog computing with artificial intelligence-driven image recognition approaches. To categorize consumption profiles the system examines visual depictions of energy data. Two different kinds of consumption profiles were identified and differentiated using Random Forest and XGBoost classifiers, allowing precise energy usage disaggregation in complex contexts.

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) developments, especially in the field of computer vision, have had a profound impact on smart environment energy management and monitoring. Conventional nonintrusive load monitoring (NILM) methods frequently call for centralized data collecting, which raises privacy issues. By allowing decentralized model training across several devices without exchanging raw data, federated learning provides an answer [1]. Federated sequence-to-sequence models have been shown in recent research to be useful in managing low-resolution, imbalanced smart meter data, improving scalability and privacy in load disaggregation methodologies [2-4].

The incorporation of non-electrical contextual data, such building characteristics, occupancy patterns, and meteorological data, is another growing field of research [5]. By offering useful priors that aid in differentiating comparable electrical loads, these characteristics may be used into NILM algorithms to greatly increase disaggregation accuracy by using probabilistic decision scenarios. For example, models can be informed by building layouts and user routines to determine when and where specific devices are likely to be in use [6-8].

Moreover, attention-based deep learning architectures have emerged as a powerful approach for NILM, particularly in addressing sequence modelling challenges inherent in

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energy disaggregation tasks [9]. By dynamically weighting relevant temporal segments and feature representations, attention mechanisms enhance the model's ability to capture complex, overlapping electrical loads [10]. This capability is especially valuable when dealing with noisy signals or low-resolution data, where traditional models often struggle to distinguish between similar load profiles.

As energy systems evolve, NILM must adapt to emerging technologies such as rooftop solar, electric vehicles, and smart batteries [11]. These elements introduce nonlinear and intermittent loads that traditional NILM models struggle to disaggregate [11]. This paper proposes a compact, image-based NILM approach designed to address several of these challenges.

The paper's four sections consist of an overview of global knowledge and the topic's applicability, an explanation of the methodology, a presentation and analysis of the findings, and closing thoughts with recommendations for further study make up.

2 Proposed Method

2.1 Data retrieval

During the experimental phase, an advanced Siemens monitoring infrastructure was used to collect numerical data on electrical energy usage in an office block that is a component of the startup network RENERGIA, which is affiliated to the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca. The dataset is made up of time-series recordings that were sampled every 30 seconds from February 27 to October 31, 2024. These recordings include active power values (in kW) and the timestamps that correspond to them.

A regulated time frame of 11:20 AM to 12:40 PM on April 29, 2024, was used to manually turn on and off several electrical equipment. The experiment was planned during a public holiday, which ensured that the building was mostly empty to reduce outside interference. To guarantee that the temporal labels appropriately reflected the actual events observed, differences between the timestamps recorded by the monitoring equipment and the system clock of the data collection server were found. As a result, all timestamps were adjusted by applying a uniform offset of 6 minutes and 30 seconds.

From the entire dataset, only intervals corresponding to one of the three target classes were selected: high-power electric kettle (>2.2 kW), two independent 2kW appliances (occasional), and other consumers. The final category was derived automatically from the remaining data, with all intervals linked to the first two classes explicitly excluded.

Time periods when an electric kettle with a rated power more than 2.2 kW was in operation were carefully chosen in order to obtain the images that corresponded to the Kettle class. These intervals were taken from a labelled Excel file and compared to the power usage curves that were recorded. Time-series consumption graphs in PNG format were automatically created using these verified segments. To preserve the raw form of the consumption curve, each image was purposefully devoid of graphic components like axes, grids, or titles and stored at a standard resolution of 64 by 64 pixels.

A new set of timestamp labels was used in a similar manner for the 2x2kW class, which focused on the period between 08:00 and 17:00. Once more, images were produced using the same graphical limitations, capturing times when there were notable correlations with the reference curves.

The Others category's selection process was entirely automated with the goal of identifying patterns that were obviously different from the recognised device energy signatures. From the remaining data, random 5-minute segments were chosen after all kettle and 2x2kW intervals were eliminated. A consumption graph was created for each, and the

Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) was used to compare it to the reference kettle profile. Only photos that showed a significant visual difference (SSIM <0.7) were kept and saved in PNG format with the same 64x64 resolution.

2.2 Data processing

For the development of the classification models, images derived from energy consumption curves were systematically processed using Python 3.9.6, along with the OpenCV, NumPy, scikit-image, and imaug libraries. The entire visual dataset generation process was carried out locally on an Apple MacBook Air system equipped with an M2 chip (8-core CPU, 16 GB RAM), running macOS Sequoia 15.2. With an average speed of 0.0439 seconds per image, the overall processing time for image generation was roughly 1.005 seconds.

In all cases the images were 32×32 pixels in size and transformed into greyscale, these were done to maintain consistency and reduce data, however, retain the unique shape of each consumption profile. Labels were assigned to images automatically from their containing path: 2 for Kettle (>2.2 kW appliances), 1 for 2x2kW (two independent 2kW selector's simultaneous on), and 0 for Other (random periods thrown away using SSIM).

In order to retain a perfect balance among the classes, the classes have been down sampled and adjusted to have the same size as the smallest group, to avoid a bias to the model learning process. We used simple data augmentation on the training images: random rotation (−10° to +10°), Gaussian noise, slight contrast manipulation (±10%) and horizontal flips (30% chance) on the input data.

Feature extraction was carried out with an HOG descriptor with 6 orientations, 4×4-pixel cells and 2×2 cell blocks. This choice allowed the classification to capture some of the important gradient patterns, even at low image resolutions.

Model assessment was conducted via stratified 5-fold cross-validation to maintain balanced class distribution in separated subsets. The training sets were the only ones which were augmented, in order not to superpose training and testing data, but to keep them strictly separated.

2.3 AI model structure

To classify the images derived from energy consumption profiles, we trained and tested two machine learning models: Random Forest and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost). These two were chosen due to their solid track record in handling multi-class problems and their compatibility with structured inputs, particularly datasets based on pre-computed features like Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG).

2.3.1 *Random Forest*

The Random Forest classifier was tuned with a set of parameters designed to strike a balance between accuracy and generalization. Specifically, we limited the number of estimators to 50 to shorten training time and reduce the likelihood of overfitting. The maximum depth for each tree was set to 5, and a minimum of three samples per leaf was required to improve robustness against noise. A fixed random seed (42) was applied to ensure that the results could be reproduced across runs.

Training was performed using HOG descriptors extracted from the augmented images. For validation, we used the corresponding non-augmented data in a 5-fold stratified cross-validation scheme. The model showed good consistency across folds and proved capable of distinguishing the characteristic consumption patterns of each class.

2.3.2 XGBoost

We use XGBoost because it is flexible and appears to perform well in binary classification problems. We tried 50 estimators, set maximum depth of trees to 2, and subsample and column sampling ratios both to 0.6 to mitigate overfitting. Further regularization was introduced by fixing gamma to 1.0. Evaluation was based on the 'logloss' metric, and use_label_encoder was set to False to maintain compatibility with the latest XGBoost versions.

On practice, XGBoost showed better both accuracy and F1 scores, especially for classes with subtle differences in HOG features with respect to the others. Both the models are trained with stratified 5-fold cross-validation with augmentation applied only to training data to avoid leakage and to obtain realistic performance estimates.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Results

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed method in identifying energy consumption patterns based on image-transformed profiles, there were trained and tested two machine learning models: Random Forest and XGBoost. These models were applied to a labelled dataset containing three distinct classes, each reflecting a specific consumption behaviour: Kettle (a high-power electric kettle, >2.2 kW), 2x2kW (two independent 2kW appliances used simultaneously) and Others (various consumers without a clearly defined profile). These images, illustrated in Fig. 1 clearly highlight the distinct visual patterns associated with each class.

To capture the morphological diversity of the consumption curves within the visual dataset, Fig. 1 present one representative example for each class. The curve in Fig. 1a, corresponding to the Kettle class, is characterized by a rapid but slightly moderated rise followed by a short plateau, typical for a high-power device with controlled activation. In Fig. 1b, associated with the 2x2kW independent class, the energy consumption profile exhibits a sharp slope, indicating the sudden simultaneous activation of two devices, each consuming approximately 2 kW. Fig. 1c illustrates a load curve from the "Others" category, without an uniform structure. This example was automatically selected based on a low SSIM score relative to the target classes, ensuring the absence of any distinctive shape.

These visual representations were used to extract Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) descriptors, which formed the foundation of the machine learning process.

Fig. 1. Load curves

Performance metrics were computed using the standard tools provided by scikit-learn. These included precision, accuracy, F1 score, and recall. Each of these was calculated per class, as well as aggregated using macro and weighted averages.

Table 1 summarizes the results obtained with the Random Forest model, which reached an average accuracy of around 88% with minimal variation across folds. The Kettle class was reliably identified, with F1 scores close to 0.90. The model also showed strong recall on the

2x2kW class, suggesting it captured well the pattern of dual simultaneous consumption. In contrast, the “Others” class proved more challenging due to its variability, resulting in lower recall and occasional misclassifications

Table 1. Random Forest performance

Fold	Accuracy	Kettle P	Kettle R	Kettle F1	2x2kW P	2x2kW R	2x2kW F1	Others P	Others R	Others F1
1	0.8831	0.87	0.92	0.90	0.84	0.95	0.89	0.96	0.78	0.86
2	0.8881	0.88	0.92	0.90	0.85	0.96	0.90	0.95	0.78	0.86
3	0.8715	0.87	0.93	0.90	0.81	0.93	0.87	0.96	0.75	0.84
4	0.877	0.87	0.91	0.89	0.83	0.96	0.89	0.96	0.76	0.85
5	0.8792	0.88	0.90	0.90	0.82	0.97	0.89	0.97	0.76	0.85

Note: P = Precision, R = Recall, F1 = F1-score

XGBoost performed slightly better overall, reaching an average accuracy of 89% (Table 2). It excelled on the 2x2kW class, with top precision and F1 scores, reflecting its ability to capture distinct patterns in this group. The Kettle class was also identified reliably, with F1 scores near 0.89. Similar to Random Forest, the “Others” class remained the hardest to classify, likely due to its internal variability.

Table 2. XGBoost performance

Fold	Accuracy	Kettle P	Kettle R	Kettle F1	2x2kW P	2x2kW R	2x2kW F1	Others P	Others R	Others F1
1	0.8853	0.85	0.93	0.89	0.87	0.92	0.90	0.94	0.80	0.87
2	0.8853	0.85	0.93	0.89	0.88	0.93	0.91	0.93	0.79	0.86
3	0.8792	0.86	0.93	0.89	0.86	0.92	0.89	0.93	0.79	0.86
4	0.8998	0.86	0.94	0.90	0.89	0.92	0.91	0.96	0.84	0.89
5	0.8842	0.87	0.91	0.89	0.84	0.95	0.89	0.96	0.79	0.87

Note: P = Precision, R = Recall, F1 = F1-score

Figures 4 and 5 show the average confusion matrices over the five cross-validation folds for Random Forest and XGBoost. These illustrate how each model distinguishes between classes and highlight common misclassifications. Random Forest tends to confuse the Others and 2x2kW classes, while XGBoost separates them more clearly, with stronger diagonals and fewer off-target predictions.

Both models performed well on the grayscale images of consumption curves, but XGBoost consistently delivered slightly better results, suggesting it generalizes more effectively for this type of visual energy pattern recognition.

Fig. 4. Random Forest aggregated confusion matrix

Fig. 5. XGBoost aggregated confusion matrix

3.2 Discussion

The results show that both Random Forest and XGBoost were able to accurately classify three distinct categories of energy consumption profile. The average accuracy values, around 88-89%, validate the proposed method. F1-scores were similar for Kettle and 2x2kW indicating that the models could differentiate between different peak consumption patterns.

The Kettle class showed consistently strong precision and recall, pointing to a clear, learnable signature. Likewise, the 2x2kW class was accurately identified across folds, with F1 scores reaching 0.90—likely due to its distinctive and stable profile shape.

On the other hand, the “Others” category proved to be more challenging. Although its precision remained high, so the models rarely confused it with other classes and the recall was lower. This indicates that many valid instances of Others were missed, which is probably due to the diversity of shapes found in this class. Because of this variation, the performance was slightly less stable, though still within acceptable limits.

Between the two models, XGBoost had a slight edge, especially in macro F1 score. Its capability to learn the complex and non-linear relationships in an organized manner may help explain this advantage. The overall difference between the two models was not dramatic and this suggests that both algorithms handled the task well given the structure of the data.

Overall, both models showed solid generalization across all five folds. By keeping a strict separation between training and test data and applying augmentation only to the training sets, the risk of overfitting was minimized. These findings highlight the potential of machine learning models to detect energy usage patterns from visual representations of consumption profiles.

Regarding the practical applications of this paper, the results presented have demonstrated the feasibility of using a single energy consumption meter at the floor level to detect the energy consumption profiles of three types of equipment within the building. These findings

can be further extended to enable the detection of differentiated energy consumption profiles for any equipment, using only one energy meter. This approach enables predictive maintenance by notifying the user when equipment is likely to be detected as faulty or nearing failure, allowing for timely replacement, an especially critical capability in environments such as data server facilities. Moreover, this solution also contributes to cost efficiency: by installing a single smart meter, users can monitor the consumption of all equipment without the need for individual meters for each device.

4 Conclusion

This study investigates the automated detection of kettle operation using just aggregate floor-level energy usage data and low-resolution pictures (64 x 64 pixels). Over the course of a nine-month test period, the system successfully recognized equipment utilization with the aid of Random Forest and XGBoost, which helped to enhance the distinctive form of each electrical load profile.

Future research will concentrate on enhancing the algorithm's capacity to identify several electrical loads running concurrently from a single aggregate energy signal, particularly those with more complicated or less recognizable load profiles.

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